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The conference will be organized in a HYBRID way, which will allow for both physical and online participation of the attendees.

The global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, and political landscape in a profound way. This century has been the scene of revolutions in information and communication technologies, enhanced economic integrations with capital mobility across readers, and a rapidly changing social environment.

In this context, **IRCOBESS 2023**'s main theme is "***New Approaches in Economics and Business: Problems & Opportunities***". In accordance with this, we welcome studies in the fields of economics and business management; also, in branches of social sciences such as public administration, politics, regional studies, and international studies that are related to economics and business management. Studies that are not within the scope of the conference will not be evaluated.

The aim of the conference is to gather leading academicians, policymakers, independent scholars, and researchers to share their knowledge, and new ideas as well as to discuss future development in these fields. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Economics, Business, and Social Sciences.

An additional goal of the **IRCOBESS 2023** is to offer an opportunity for young researchers, academicians, and practitioners with multidisciplinary interests to meet and interact with members inside and outside their own particular disciplines.

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS DETERMINING THE VALUE MOTIVATIONAL SPHERE OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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ABSTRACT

Women entrepreneurs and women businesswomen are generally characterized by the following personality traits and qualities. Possessing these qualities, women by nature feel particularly confident in the financial structure. They are meticulous and scrupulous in their ability to count money. Women are successful when it comes to researching a company's position in the market.

In work, women's perseverance and attentiveness, purposefulness and accuracy are well known. Rationality and flexibility of thinking, ability to analyze and evaluate, readiness to make decisions, openness and social competence - these are the qualities inherent in a woman and necessary for her as an entrepreneur and manager.

In this article we will talk about thoughts and reasoning about the components of the psychology of a modern woman entrepreneur.

INDEX TERMS

Woman, modern, entrepreneur, entrepreneur, psychology, business, money, virtue.

Women's success in entrepreneurship and business depends on their ability to turn a "want" into a "need". For them, "want" is the embodiment of freedom in their affairs, thoughts and destinies. Turning a "want" into a "need" helps them successfully solve another important problem: the problem of the "long box," overcoming the temptation to put off" something unpleasant or annoying.

And so that this" box "does not hang on them the sword of Damocles and does not" press on the psyche, they are very quickly dismantled and know that success accompanies a person who does not always do what he wants, but always does what he wants.

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Turning" a need "into" a want "helps them to successfully solve another important problem: it is the problem of" the long box", overcoming the temptation to postpone" something unpleasant or boring". And so that this" box "does not hang on them the sword of Damocles and does not" pressure on the psyche, they are very quickly dismantled and know that success accompanies a person who does not always do what he wants, but always does what he wants.

To succeed in business, it is very important to understand your relationship to money. Power, authority, fame, glory, success, prosperity, mercy, kindness, generosity-all of these are money. What a particular person sees in it depends only on him.

A certain business man, even the richest, has a certain amount of money, and others own everything, the ability to feel comfortable in such a reality determines the psychological peace of a businesswoman, she can invest (invest) in the development of society, in good deeds, such is the nature of money.

They require from a man a firm attitude to himself. And they pay him the same way. If they are mistreated, they go to another.

Money can be the root of all problems and failures. They are capable of destroying people's psyche. By accumulating wealth and not letting it turn into a business, a person kills hundreds of other people. When one finds out what a person's relationship to money is, it becomes clear why he has so much of it. Like the echoes of a mountain, money gives him back what he thinks he has, returns as the equivalent of rational effort expended. It is very important to achieve long-term success in business to make money in an honest way and to make sure that the current business is beneficial to people. Following these conditions allows businesswomen to live up to their self and money becomes their joy. Good deeds do not go unnoticed by society, they increase prestige, attract customers and ensure commercial success of business activities.

In a study conducted by the think tank, the women surveyed found that work allows them to be creative, entrepreneurial and deserving of respect from friends, family and relatives. But these influential last points don't matter much. For women, the idea that work motives are extrinsic and work is less meaningful is disturbing and nourishing. Women's professional status is influenced by their marital status, the need to combine roles, which limits the choice of activities, makes it difficult to advance in their careers, and creates difficulties in work. 1/3 of respondents noted high nervous load, 14% of women and 19% of workers reported fatigue due to homework and childhood illnesses.

Thus, professional difficulties fall on women's overload at work and at home. Hence fatigue and constant nervous tension, fear of not being on time, fear of failing, etc. Of course, all these leading circumstances make it difficult for women to fully participate in professional activities.

First, there is a deep awareness of equal rights, equal opportunities and the ability to participate in all spheres of society. Another important characteristic is the recognition of the need to combine different social roles - not only an active participant in work and public life, but also a "housekeeper" and mother. Women choose different combinations of these roles, although many of them are oriented towards their equal importance.

A woman chooses her life path in accordance with her personal qualities, preferences, tastes and life circumstances, but the possibility of such a choice depends on the economic and moral support provided by the state and society for each path she chooses.

To summarize, we can say that even the most advanced social practices cannot negate the psychological difficulties arising from the "double" employment of women at work and at home.

The equal position of women in society significantly changes the traditional idea of such qualities as masculinity and femininity. Women possess forms of behavior previously attributed to men, such as the ability to make decisions, assert their opinions, and independence

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